

SRINIVAS UNIVERSITY

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Institute of Allied Health Science

CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABDUL RAHEEM V bearing USN 6SU20MI001 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ABHISHA S AJITH bearing USN 6SU20MI002 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms ADIL RAHMAN bearing USN 6SU20MI003 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms AHAMMED SHAMIL P bearing USN 6SU20MI004 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms AJAYKRISHNAN K V bearing USN 6SU20MI005 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASNA E T P bearing USN 6SU20MI006 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWANI SATHEESAN N P bearing USN 6SU20MI007 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms ASWATHI P K bearing USN 6SU20MI008 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms BLESSON ABRAHAM bearing USN 6SU20MI009 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms DANI VARGHESE bearing USN 6SU20MI010 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms EDWIN K RAJU bearing USN 6SU20MI011 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms GAIUS SALEM THAMPI bearing USN 6SU20MI012 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms JOSE P JOSEPH bearing USN 6SU20MI013 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMAD NIDHAL bearing USN 6SU20MI014 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms MUHAMMED NIHAL M P bearing USN 6SU20MI015 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms NANDANA N bearing USN 6SU20MI016 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms PARVANA SREELAL bearing USN 6SU20MI017 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SANDRA SANTHOSH T P bearing USN 6SU20MI018 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHABEEB CHENNAT bearing USN 6SU20MI019 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SHRADDHA N PUTHRAN bearing USN 6SU20MI020 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SIDHARTH K P bearing USN 6SU20MI021 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms SREYA bearing USN 6SU20MI022 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms THOMASKUTTY JOY bearing USN 6SU20MI023 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHNU P S bearing USN 6SU20MI024 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that Mr/Ms VISHNU VENU bearing USN 6SU20MI025 has completed his/her internship at Srinivas Hospital Mangalore in the first Semester of the Bsc. Medical Imaging Technology programme for the academic year 2020-2021

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